

Table 1: Questions used to carry out the quality assessment according to Kitechnham et al.

ID	Question	Weight
Q1	Are the goals clearly formulated?	5
Q2	Which population was investigated?	1
Q3	Are the measures used in the study fully defined?	4
Q4	Are the methods of data collection adequately described?	4
Q5	Did no unwanted events occur during the study?	2
Q6	Have the basic data been adequately described?	3
Q7	Are the statistical methods described?	3
Q8	Is the purpose of the analysis clear?	5
Q9	Were no side effects reported?	1
Q10	Have all the study questions been answered?	1
Q11	Do the researchers explain the consequences of problems with the validity/reliability of their measurements?	2
Q12	What are the implications of the findings for practice?	2

Supplementary material for the submission: Linda Gauder, Christian Kücherer, Denise Junger, Oliver Burgert: Elicitation and Documentation of Explainability Requirements in a Medical Information Systems Context. Submitted to ICSE 2025.

1 Appendix

To provide further information, this appendix contains additional tables and graphics that support the content explained above. Firstly, this includes the questions for the quality assessment of the systematic mapping studies in table 1. This is followed by the element descriptions with definition questions for each element of the sentence template in Table 2 to 3. Additional research data can be downloaded at the EUs zenodo portal <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10854275>.

1.1 Questions for quality

We used following questions to define the studies quality. Number in brackets give the weight, and the final quality score is given in tab. 1.

1.2 Element definition for sentence template

Table 2 gives details about the types of addressees with questions for requirements completeness.

Table 2: Description of <type of addressee> with examples of definition aids and questions to aid understanding.

Element	Description
Developer	person who contributes to the creation of the software.
Consumer	person who buys the system for later use.
Users	person who uses the system
Stakeholder	person who has an interest in the system
Partner	person who participates in the creation of the system.
Employee	person who works for the organisation or company that creates the system
Questions on the definition of information	Who are the relevant target groups and what are their specific characteristics? What are the relevant desiderata in a particular context and are they being met? Is the information really useful/helpful for the target group?

Table 3: Description of the property <explainer> with associated examples of definition help and questions to aid understanding.

Element	Description
AI that explains itself	Is a system way of creating the explanation, through an AI.
Explainability Tool	Is a system possibility to create the explanation by a tool
Humans	Is a system possibility to create the explanation, by a human
Information definition questions	Is the explanation approach able to pass on the information through a suitable source that promotes the understanding of the target group? Is the information really useful/helpful for the target group?

Table 4: Description of the property <aspect> with associated examples of definition help and questions to aid understanding

Element	Description
White-Box Systems Creation	improve the interpretability methods of white-box models
Black-Box Systems Explanation	To improve the interpretability of black-box models
Increase fairness of the system	Interpretability of the system is related to the social and ethical implications of algorithms in terms of fairness and evaluates the system for impartiality and discrimination of users.
Checking sensitivity of prediction	The trustworthiness of predictions/results of the system need to be assessed for their stability.
Evaluating the impact	The system has an impact on society. Here, the evaluation of the impact should be explained
Gain user confidence	The explanation of the system to the target group is of decision to gain their trust.
Increase security of the systems	Ensuring transparency through explanations can strain data protection.
Increase traceability	The system should be comprehensible in all areas and be able to explain the individual decisions that lead up to the result.
Increase comprehensibility	The purpose of comprehensibility is to convey to people the where and why of the use of the system, as well as to make the system as such comprehensible
Purpose of the system	The purpose of the system must be clearly defined and relates primarily to the how and why of the system's use
Role and capability of the system	It must be defined when the system gives recommendations and when it gives a clear decision
Inputs of the system	The inputs used in the system should be presented
Outputs of the system	The outputs received in the system should be presented
Behaviour of the system	The behaviour of the system should include information about how the system works
Algorithms of the system	The representation of the algorithms, especially the inner workings of them, should be reproduced.
Data used by the system	The data used within the system must be represented. This mainly refers to where and how the data is used. Also the accuracy of the data used
Constraints of the system	Should show how far reaching the system is in terms of boundaries
Model-specific	Shall set whether the explanation can be applied to a single area.
Model-agnostic	Shall set whether the explanation can be applied to any area.
Structure of the explanation	The structure is composed of several attributes. Shall define which attributes can be appropriately chosen within the target group and context for the explanation
Information definition questions	Has the target group acquired a sufficient level and the right kind of understanding to be able to judge whether certain wishes are fulfilled and to facilitate their fulfilment? Is the information really useful/helpful for the target group?

Table 5: Description of the property <context> with associated examples of definition help and questions to aid understanding.

Element	Description
Local	Defines an explanation that addresses individual cases in the system
Global	Defines an explanation that involves the entire system.
Causal/Mechanical	It is defined by the relationship, A causes B to do C.
Functional/Technological	It is defined by the relationship, A did B because of function C.
Intentional	It is defined by the relationship, A did B because C wanted or needed it.
Documentation Form	Defines the form-type of explanation: textual, audible, numerical, rule-based or mixed, containing several types of explanations.
Counterfactual Explanation	Is a representation of the explanation that refers to what is not given
Conflict Relationship	Is a representation of the explanation that supports the explanation of how conditions can be influenced.
Correlation coefficients	Is a representation of the explanation that conveys the relationship between two variables through the correlation coefficient.
Other	The representations of the explanation can differ from the possibilities mentioned and it is possible to formulate the explanation under a different aspect.
Information definition questions	Are there contextual influences that can hinder or promote the satisfaction of the desiderata by the explanatory process? Is the explanatory approach able to provide the right type and amount of explanatory information in the right form of presentation? Is the information really useful/helpful for the target group?